

Business Opportunities for Beyond 5G and 6G Networks

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Abstract—In this work, we intend to present various aspects of the business model associated with technology. We presented a detailed description of beyond 5G and 6G networks with the potential use cases and applications. We mapped the use cases to different potential business opportunities. We also described why Network slicing is an essential enabler for future networks and its importance for creating new businesses. We stressed the multi-business model approach to defining the business model concerning Network slicing and other applications. Thus, this paper will address the business value creation through technology for the beyond 5G and 6G networks.

Index Terms—Beyond 5G, 6G, Network Slicing, 6G Use Cases, Holographic Communication, Business Models, Multi-Business Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the deployment of the Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks, we are witnessing the advancing research and development towards the Sixth Generation (6G) networks. Academia and industry joined hands to support the timely development and deployment. 5G networks offered massive connectivity, higher bandwidth, minimal latency, and several services and applications as an advantage over its predecessor. The expectations from 6G networks are even higher; for instance, sensory experience, interactive communications through holograms, and the internet of the networks [1]. It assures an energy-efficient, reliable, robust, and secure platform that will open up opportunities for new businesses. 6G networks have the potential and capability to support diverse verticals with varied requirements. These varying requirements need optimized and blended techniques and algorithms with built-in intelligence to enable different parallel applications.

The core requirement from 6G networks includes spectrum/resource management techniques, broader bandwidth, and a new radio spectrum to achieve higher data rates and lower latency. The estimated data rates and latency can be around the scale of Terabit/second and 0.1 milliseconds, respectively. The Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) introduced 5G Service Based Architecture (SBA) [2] to support the coexistence of heterogeneous network requirements in its technical specification 23.501 [3]. SBA incorporates a scalable, flexible, cost-efficient, and programmable platform

to accommodate simultaneous services. SBA enables Network Functions (NF) and facilitates Network Function Virtualization (NFV) to provide services to other authorized NFs, through APIs, cloud technologies, and a client-server model. NFV, Software Defined Network (SDN), and cloud computing technologies allow the creation of “Network Slices” over a shared physical network infrastructure. The technology to create logically isolated slices is called Network Slicing (NS) [4] and facilitates end-to-end connectivity [5]. The Communication Service Providers (CSPs) can cater to diverse user-specific demands through slicing with guaranteed Quality-of-Service (QoS). The main advantage of deploying NS is that no new physical network is required for dedicated services. CSPs take advantage of network orchestration and virtualization to provide real-time services based on the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) [6].

The development of 6G technology needs a holistic and multidimensional approach to integrate technologies and support businesses to flourish. 6G defines an integrated network with built-in control systems that execute technologies for societal, environmental, and economic benefit. 6G systems are advocating more towards a sustainable solution. Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) intend to create new businesses and business models for the advancing technologies. A 5G and beyond network will have a user-centric approach toward business models and aim to solve the issues of the customers [7]. Changes in the Telecom landscape are evident and reflected through the value and supply chain revolution. The deployment of 5G is eminent among public networks and is being embraced in diversified industrial and consumer use cases. 6G development will drive the supply chain transformation to allow new verticals to establish. It is essential to focus on the business value creation in addition to the customers’ needs and challenges. 6G will redefine the creation, delivery, and consumption of network resources and services, irrespective of the verticals and applications [8]. Thus, this paper will address the business value creation through technology for the beyond 5G and 6G networks.

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The remaining paper is organized as follows. Section II will highlight beyond 5G and 6G technologies and use cases from a business creation perspective. Section III will explain further the mapping of beyond 5G and 6G use cases to businesses. Section IV will introduce the business modeling concept. Finally, Section V presents the conclusions and open research areas.

II. BEYOND 5G AND 6G NETWORKS

Juniper's research article [9] cites that the 5G voice users will surpass the 2.5 billion mark by 2026. 5G New Radio (5G NR) architecture supports simultaneous use cases in heterogeneous scenarios [10]. The essential building blocks for 5G networks are defined by the following three categories of use case classes: (i) enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), (ii) Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), and (iii) massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC). In a nutshell, (i) eMBB services demand very high peak data rates, (ii) mMTC supports massive connective devices/nodes, and (iii) URLLC supports ultra-low latency requirements and high reliability. These characteristic features will also form the basis for 6G research and development.

A. Network Slicing as 6G Enabler

6G systems will evolve on the 5G SBA architecture [2] [3] to meet the core requirements, including spectrum/resource management techniques, broader bandwidth, and a new radio spectrum to achieve higher data rates and lower latency. SBA enables Network Slicing to facilitate end-to-end connectivity and user-specific services [5]. The CSPs and MNOs exhibit guaranteed QoS in catering to user demands for specific services. Beyond 5G and 6G networks intend to have a user-centric approach toward business models and aim to solve the issues of the customers [7] and operators. These networks aim for the flexible, agile, and scalable core in addition to the leverage of implementing new services on-demand by the CSPs and MNOs. The Figure 1 illustrates the operators' requirements for the upcoming generation of wireless communication [11].

Virtualization techniques and cloud technologies enabled the network to have independent network functions [12]. The vendors must have the usage flexibility in computation, storage, and accessibility to private/public clouds to reduce both CAPEX and OPEX. Network Slicing (NS) is seen as the solution from both an architecture and business perspective [13]. 3GPP introduced the slicing framework in Release 15 [14], which gradually matured in the following releases. It supports multiple virtual network instances operating on the same physical hardware and provides varying individual services to slices [4]. It allows MNOs to partition the networks to cater to specific service requests. SDN, NFV, orchestration, and service provisioning together enable NS architecture. The SDN facilitates the control and user plane separation, where the physical resources are virtualized, implementing NFV. Organizations like the Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA) [15] and Next-Generation Mobile Network (NGMN) [4] are constantly involved in defining standards for

Fig. 1. Requirements Mapping from Operators' Perspective for 6G Networks [11]

slicing framework and architecture. 3GPP has various study groups that monitor and regulate NS standardization activities in specific areas like requirements, use cases, NS Architecture, slice creation, and security [16] [17]. GSMA and NGMN are also involved in defining the business drivers and requirements together with the MNOs and CSPs [18].

B. Application Areas and Use Cases

Future networks will have more versatile and diversified demands in addition to the constantly evolving use cases based on the service requirements and new businesses [19]. On the societal side, 6G applications are foreseen to address collaboration, digital equity, and social sustainability challenges. 6G network design aims to reduce CO2 emissions and improve energy efficiency [20], [21].

Authors in [21] have defined the following classes as illustrated in Figure 2 for the 6G use cases. The Next G Alliance report [20] on "6G Applications and Use Cases" has provided different categories for the 6G applications and use cases.

The fig 3 illustrates the categories of 6G applications while the four sub-classes for the use cases are: (i) Network-Enabled Robotics and Autonomous Systems, (ii) Multi-sensory Extended Reality, (ii) Distributed Sensing and Communications, and (iv) Personalized User Experiences.

C. Technical Requirements for the Use Cases [20], [22]

This section briefly covers the system requirements for the 6G use cases. 6G networks are expected to support existing 5G services, applications and tools as well. Some of the basic requirements [20] that 6G networks should allow for facilitating coexistence must include the support for voice calls, messaging, 5G handoffs, and security and privacy by design. The ITU-T [23] also has published system requirements for

Fig. 2. High-level Use Cases Categorization [21]

Everyday Living	Applications to improve daily quality of living.
Experience	Applications dedicated to enhancing user experience and enabling immersive communication.
Critical Roles	The 6G applications that aid critical functions in healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture, and public safety are categorized under this vertical.
Societal Goals	This category includes 6G applications that cater to overall societal, environmental, and economic issues. These also align with 17 UN Sustainable goals.

Fig. 3. High-level Categorization of 6G Applications [21]

Network 2030. The Key Parameter Indicators (KPI) for 6G are illustrated in Figure 4 as a comparison with the 5G networks [22].

KPI	5G	6G
Operating Bandwidth	400 MHz (sub-6 GHz bands) 3.25GHz (mmWave bands)	400 MHz (sub-6 GHz bands) 3.25GHz (mmWave bands) 10-100 GHz [Indicative] (THz bands)
Carrier Bandwidth	400 MHz	To be defined
Peak Data Rate	20 Gbps	≥1 Tbps
User Experience Rate	100 Mbps	1 Gbps
Average Spectral Efficiency	7.8 bps/Hz (DL) 5.4 bps/Hz (UL)	1 x that of 5G
Connection Density	10 ⁶ devices/km ²	10 ⁷ devices/km ²
User Plane Latency	4 ms (eMBB) 1 ms (uRLLC)	25 μs to 1 ms
Control Plane Latency	20 ms	20 ms
Mobility	500 km/h	1000 km/h
Mobility Interruption Time	0 ms (uRLLC)	0 ms

Fig. 4. KPIs Mapping of 6G Networks

- Holographic Type Communication (HTC) is foreseen as one of the key evolutions to enable the immersive three-dimensional experience. HTC blends the audio/visual transmission with multi-sensory data, including touch, smell, and taste [24]. High computational capabilities,

compression techniques, ultra-high data rates, and ultra-low latency are essential requirements for interactive holographic communications [25], [26] [27]. A human-sized hologram demands a data rate of around 4.3 Tb/s and sub-millisecond latency. Synchronization and security will be critical in the real-time integration of various scenarios and sensor feeds.

- Industrial Automation: 6G will witness a revolution in manufacturing industries fostered by human-machine in Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) [28]. These massively connected machine interactions, robotics, and remote management-control of industrial systems are essentials of Industry 4.0. Ultra-low latency of 0.1 ms and ultra-high reliability [29] guarantees real-time monitoring and control to enable high Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE). VR or HTC integration into Industry 4.0 will enable remote monitoring/control services. Based on the application requirement, data rate varies from 1–5 Mb/s (1080p high-definition video), 15–25 Mb/s (4K 360 degree video) to a whopping 0.5–2 Gb/s (small holograms) up to 4.2 Tb/s for human-sized holograms [22]. Latency in order of 1ms to submillisecond, high-end synchronization, and security to avoid hazards and life threats.
- Service Robots for Healthcare: With the recent advancements, robotic applications will play a key role in various aspects of human lives. After demonstrating their significance in manufacturing and industrial automation, robots can enhance our everyday lives. 6G will see the rise of Service Robots [20] with ambient intelligence to enhance everyday activities (caregiving, travel assistance, ambient assisted living), healthcare pursuits (surgery robots), and critical roles (search and rescue operations, firefighter training). Field robots will be helpful in monitoring and maintaining hard-to-access locations. A very high level of clock synchronization and ultra-low latency, high reliability, accuracy in positioning and localization, self-healing techniques, and shorter re-establish time in connection failures are critical requirements for the service robots.
- Multi-Sensory Extended Reality (XR) Interactive Sports (Drone Racing): Drone racing is an example to catalog the potential of the 6G network in a highly interactive scenario. the first drone racing was exhibited in the World Drone Prix, Dubai (2016) [30] using the 5G network. With 6G, in a 360-degree spherical display, it is expected to have more than 2x16K resolution images with a latency of less than 20 ms. The image resolution and latency are critical parameters of drone racing. A transmission data rate varies from a minimum of 60 Mbps (8K screen), 2 Gbps (16K screen), and 4 Gbps to stream 2x16K with 6 Degree of Freedom (DoF [20]). Throughput, latency, and mobility are essentials for this use case.

III. MAPPING OF BEYOND 5G AND 6G ESSENTIALS TO BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES [1], [20] [26]

The recent advancements have resulted in the multidimensional integration of industrial verticals. There are enormous opportunities for businesses to grow and integrate cutting-edge technologies. Integrating technology in business to provide solutions intends to bring added value to customers and industries. This section will map various use cases and applications to potential business opportunities beyond 5G and 6G networks.

a) **Networked-enabled Robotics:** Networked robotics is critically important for Industry 4.0 and beyond, providing an additional layer of benefits for enterprises and related industries. It also is necessary for some critical factors that our daily living environments have already begun to face. The following is a list of societal implications of networked robotics.

- 1) **Manufacturing and Logistic Industry** Industrial robots have massive potential in production and operation management industries.
- 2) **Human Resource Management** Robots are proving their efficiency in performing scheduled tasks like mobile inspection and maintenance at remote locations.
- 3) **Retirement Homes** Robots can be deployed to provide care to older adults. It can also be used to monitor basic health parameters. Interactive robots are even used to provide ambient assisted living.

b) **Multi-sensory XR:** Interactive XR capabilities converging AR/VR technologies have huge potential in services that provide immersive real-time experiences.

- 1) **Interactive Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)** Self-connected and configurable drones are helpful in verticals like agriculture and transportation.
- 2) **Immersive Communication** has huge potential in realizing new standards for long-distance and remote interactions through XR conferencing and holographic communication.
- 3) **Mixed Reality Collaborations** has found new definitions to provide co-creation platforms in education, training, music concerts, etc.

c) **Distributed Sensing:** These use cases enable autonomous systems with sensors coupled with communications.

- 1) **Remote Data Collection** IoT industries are utilized in health care, smart homes, education, and logistic tracking systems for data collection for various applications.
- 2) **Healthcare-Wearables and Implants** There is an exponential rise in the number of wearables to monitor daily activities like heart rate, sleep, steps, and stress levels.

IV. INTRODUCTION TO BUSINESS MODELS

A Business Model (BM) represents a business in an abstract form to depict a company's plan to maximize its profit [31]. It entails an organization's blueprint to create, deliver, and capture value, considering various factors. As cited by Ericsson [32] beyond 5G, and 6G networks enable various new

Fig. 5. Business Opportunities in different Industries

business opportunities in the telecom sector sectors in the top 60%. Figure 5 [32] illustrates different industries with business opportunities. BM represents a high-level business plan based on the target market. A value proposition, an essential entity of a BM, describes the offered services/products considering customers' requirements and overall impact. It refers to the promises made by the company toward customers.

Fig. 6. Multi Business Model Innovation Illustration

This section describes the Multi Business Model Innovation approach [33] to map business opportunities associated with 6G networks and network slicing. Figure 6 illustrates various verticals of a business model from customer-end to the provider-end. This model helpful in creating and capturing essentials of the "AS IS" BM and maps the requirements of "TO BE" BMs. It explains a general model to run a business with profit. Its different arms as mentioned below and in Figure 6 shows perspective to create BM from different angles.

- 1) **Value Propositions** includes the promises made by the MNOs and CSPs toward customers. It involves the processes and different product and services offered to

the customer. For instance; ultra-high bandwidth support to enable real-time multiplayer gaming experience.

- 2) **Value Formula** covers the company's expenses and give profit or loss numbers. It also includes installation and maintenance costs.
- 3) **Value Chain Functions** describes all the tasks involved to create a product or service.
- 4) **User and Customer** includes either or both of the B2B or B2C model to capture the relationship matrix between users and providers.
- 5) **Networks** denote the channel through which services or products reach its desired customers.
- 6) **Competences** capture the technological advancements including tangible and non-tangible resources.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OPEN RESEARCH AREA

There are many technical and commercial bottlenecks with the NS implementation. The main challenge is to manage standardization associated with the network slices in generating new businesses, where industrial giants come together. On the one hand, where NS brings flexibility and connectivity to various industrial verticals, it demands revolutionary changes in every aspect of operations (integrating automation and intelligence). Network slicing provides MNOs, CSPs, and industries with the most needed value proposition to create new business models. The value creation depends on the service and applied configurations [1]. The telco giants control the end-to-end value chain in Business-to-Customer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B) sectors.

Resource Management will also be critical in specific applications with rigid bandwidth, latency, and computation requirements. The spectrum is an expensive and scarce resource. Thus, enabling critical services with dedicated resources can be expensive. Other critical and open issues include QoS associated with roaming and inter-slice security. Roaming that fails due to a lack of established standards and security becomes critical when we have services delivered by different operators with varying security protocols on shared physical infrastructure. Developing new businesses need clarity in the requirements like service life-cycle, resource allocation (estimated and actual), and other varying parameters like leasing costs and SLAs. Some identified challenges associated with slicing and slices include mobility, dynamic slice creation/management, QoS, slice isolation, handovers, and latency. Apart from technical bottlenecks, we have regulatory challenges that include business ethics, political (geographical regions) and governmental laws.

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